

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School
Address: Ermin Garcia St, corner EDSA,
Brgy. Pinagkaisahan, Quezon City
Tel No: (02) 637 6754

Process Structure and Material Analysis of Project Buoyani: A Review

A Capstone Project
made for the Fulfillment
of the Requirement in
**Work Immersion for Senior
High School Students**

MARC ANDRIE M. BERMUNDO
Proponent

ENGR. NOEL JANDUSAY
Work Immersion Teacher

12 – STEM Archimedes

SY 2020 - 2021

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¹Marc Andrie M. Bermundo & ²Engr. Noel Jandusay
¹Proponent & ²Work Immersion Teacher

Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School - Senior High School Department

ABSTRACT

Project Buoyani is a buoy that is currently under the development of start-up company Team Maharlika. The portmanteau word came from two words, “buoy” and “bayani”, and was an original idea that came from the fruition of joining the hackathon by Oceana Philippines and Department of Science and Technology - Advanced Science and Technology Institute (DOST - ASTI) named “Karagathon: A Hackathon to Combat Illegal Fishing in the Philippines”. The buoy is intended to focus on monitoring municipal waters with low-cost and efficient materials that can easily relay information to the authorities in the nearest area where the buoy is located. In this study, the researcher, a founding member of Team Maharlika, decides to check upon the initial process structure of the project as well as analyzing the materials that are necessary for the creation of this buoy. This includes checking all the payloads that are going to be used for the project, the mechanism in order to power it at sea, and the communication systems that it will use in order to notify the authorities about what is happening at the moment. All of the results on what will be the used materials for this project is strictly classified by the researcher for privacy.

Keywords: *buoy system, process structure, Buoyani*

INTRODUCTION

Karagathon is a hackathon of software solutions that will help combat illegal fishing in the Philippines. It is organized by Oceana Philippines with the help and support of the Department of Agriculture (DA), the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR), and the Department of Science and Technology - Advanced Science and Technology Institute (DOST - ASTI).

KARAGATHON
A HACKATHON TO COMBAT ILLEGAL FISHING IN THE PHILIPPINES

Deadline to Apply
JULY 15, 2020
Karagathon Period
AUGUST 1 - 30, 2020
Announcement of Winners
SEPTEMBER 4, 2020

Grand Prize
P100,000

To know more and apply:
karagatanpatrol.org/karagathon

Oceana Philippines
30 June 2020

Are you tech-savvy with the heart to help the ocean and our fisherfolk? If yes, then it's your time to shine!

Oceana presents the first ever Karagathon, the search for the most innovative ideas that can help fight illegal fishing in the Philippines. The winning concept from this competition will complement Karagatan Patrol, an online platform for reporting illegal fishing activities.

To know more and apply, visit
<http://karagatanpatrol.org/karagathon/>

Karagathon is suppor... See more

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KARAGATHON
A Hackathon to Combat Illegal Fishing in the Philippines

5 DAYS LEFT TO APPLY
Deadline: July 15, 2020

Grand Prize
P100,000

Oceana Philippines
11 July 2020

5 days left to apply for the first ever #Karagathon! Karagathon is a codefest that aims to find the most innovative solutions that can help end illegal fishing in the Philippines. To learn more and apply, visit karagatanpatrol.org/karagathon

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Figure 1.1 – 1.4: The announcement and application periods of the Karagathon competition in the Facebook page of Oceana Philippines.
 (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The competition is a hackathon with a mission to search for the most innovative ideas that can help fight illegal fishing in the Philippines. The winning concept from this competition will complement Karagatan Patrol, an online platform for reporting illegal

fishing activities. The Karagatan Patrol is a Facebook group where authorities and private people and organizations (like Oceana Philippines) are posting about experiences on protecting the coastal waters as well as coastal police (Bantay Dagat) updates.

In the first ever Karagathon, senior high school students from Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School that are comprised of Erwin B. Bonto (Team Leader), Marc Andrie M. Bermundo, Justin Alexis B. Versoza, Julius Rafael V. Ele, and Cassia Cyrus C. Olmon, have joined under the name of "Team Maharlika". Team Maharlika had unveiled their first project during this competition, named as Buoyani. The portmanteau word came from two words, "buoy" and "bayani", thus forming Buoyani.

Figure 1.5: The final announcement for the submission of applications in the first Karagathon competition in the Facebook page of Oceana Philippines.
(Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

The function of this buoy focuses on monitoring municipal waters with low-cost and efficient materials that can (1) easily relay information to the authorities in the nearest area where the buoy is located with the objectives of developing a buoy system that delivers accurate and precise data from different detection and ranging sensors to a systematic database, (2) assist the authorities by providing real time information coming

from incoming fishing vessels around the buoy's range of detection, (3) providing surveillance for the said fishing vessels by equipping hidden cameras to the buoy, and (4) tracking down fishing vessels around the buoy's range of detection using real time kinematic global positioning system (GPS).

The promising proposition of the Buoyani had made it to the Top 15 of the selected people to join and propagate their project under the course of the competition. However, Team Maharlika did not win the finals. The winners for the first ever Karagathon are Parrotfish.net, Hydraean, and Oceans 13 (Mod 7).

Figure 1.6: The logo of Project Buoyani. (Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Despite being defeated in the said competition, there are still plans for the said project. In this research paper, one of the members of Team Maharlika will look upon first the process structure and materials analysis of the project. To be specific, this project only limits itself with the range of plans that are specially specified to the members of Team Maharlika, ergo limiting it only to the basic process structure of the Buoyani. All of the results, however, is stringently confidential to the team only.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Definition of Illegal Fishing

According to Hanson (2021), illegal fishing is a breach of any regulation that is required for fishing. Because fishing is one of the oldest occupations, it is carefully monitored and controlled in most modern societies in order to use natural resources most efficiently. It generally requires a license or permit and is allowed only on certain bodies of water at certain times of year. Local governments only allow certain types of fish and fish of certain sizes can be legally caught.

Most of the states and countries monitors the permit for fishermen that will fish in their local areas. The purpose of this action is to place a limit upon the number of people engaged in fishing but is primarily a means of generating revenue, which is often used to fund the governmental agencies responsible for overseeing and managing fish and wildlife.

Figure 2.2: A commercial fishing vessel used for acquiring large quantities of fish in the sea. (Source: boatsonline.com.au)

Illegal fishing come in varieties, with the most common being fishermen lacking the permits needed in order to fish in a specific area. It can also involve the use of prohibited fishing techniques.

In an article published by Rinkesh (2018), there are many methods of prohibited fishing techniques that are damaging to the environment where the fish live as well as the health of the fishes themselves. The methods of fishing that are stated in the article include bottom trawling, bycatch, blast fishing, ghost fishing, cyanide fishing, muro ami, kayakas, overfishing, electro-fishing, dumping of substances, and keeping undersized or oversized fish.

Bottom trawling is an industrial technique that uses huge nets weighed down with weighty ballast that gets hauled down the sea bed, amassing and squashing the whole lot that is on the way, from fish to marine plants. The collateral damage, also mentioned to as discards, can go up to 80% or 90%.

In addition, big parts of the seafloor, the territories where fish live and look for food, get compressed during the process. The nets that are used in this devastating technique can leave scars on the seafloor that may range up to four kilometers in length.

Figure 2.2: Bottom trawling of an industrial boat in a European sea.
(Source: terremajeure.com)

It also stirs up sediment that may be noxious, with chances of generating murky water that gives aquatic species a problematic time living. This treacherous method of fishing is mostly used by industrial boats in the deeper areas in the seas, sometimes it is

even regulated in some areas. In addition, it has been held responsible as a large contributor to the act of overfishing and often used for fishing in verboten marine areas.

Bycatch on the other hand, means accidentally catching numerous types of aquatic life in the progression of catching other fish. Bycatches vary in what they are, such as the wrong size of the intended fish, and other creatures that do not get eaten or the ones which are not in demand during the season, as well as species that are nearing extinction, consisting of birds, aquatic mammals, and turtles.

Figure 2.3: A marine turtle being trapped in fishing nets as a result of a bycatch.
(Source: Michel Gunther / WWF - Canon)

While bycatching disdains other sea creatures being jammed in the fishing nets, keeping undersized or oversized fish is also considered to be illicit, as regulations only authorizes a certain threshold for the catch that is gained by the boats. This will give time for the fish in order for them to repopulate. If protocols were not approved on the number of fish that is necessary to be caught, it will leave a negative impact on marine biodiversity.

The act of deliberate abandonment of fishing objects in a water body is called ghost fishing. The fishing nets that are left by the fishermen still continue to catch fish and other

creatures, by which they die out eventually due to fatigue or being smothered. This issue may be addressed by new and artificial fibers used for fishing in order to lessen the amount of fishing nets that are discarded in the open water because of the robustness that is existing in these newer materials.

Blast fishing is mostly used by fishermen to illegally catch fish with the use of an explosive (typically dynamite) that may abolish the sea bed with a range of 10 - 20 m². Alongside with killing the intended fishes, they also kill unwanted species as well as coral reef formations. These formations may take up a hundred years just to regenerate.

Figure 2.4: An example of blast fishing, commonly known as dynamite fishing.
(Source: cleanmalaysia.com)

In conjunction with a prevalent illegitimate fishing technique, *muro-ami*, this procedure is extensively used by fishermen especially in the Southeast Asian region. This is done by a huge encircling net with a number of pounding tools, normally cement blocks or huge stones that are attached on the exterior to pound fish out of coral reefs. Characteristically, fish aren't scared of the drubbing, but the effect of losing their habitat may drive fish away and get caught. Alongside with blast fishing methods, this will

definitely damage the formations that are done by corals, leaving the biodiversity of the marine area being unlawfully fished to be destroyed or be gone for a long time.

A slightly reduced version but still perilous and unlawful variant of *muro-ami* is called *kayakas*. This is also referred to as *bahan*, *bahiglukay*, *lukayan*, *gill net*, *ring net*, or *bahan*. It utilizes tree trunks and plant branches or even coconut leaves and other similar constituents as scarelines to make the fish go out of its habitation.

Figure 2.5: A part of the process of the muro-ami. Here, the diver prepares the scarelines for the fish to come out of the coral reefs. (Source: Mongabay)

First used in the Philippines throughout the 1960's to catch live fish for retailing to export it to other countries, cyanide fishing uses crushed cyanide tablets into plastic squirt bottles of water to acquire live fishes that are hiding in the reefs. Some reports state that this method is still being used in providing fish for Hong Kong and Singapore restaurants.

Another type of illegal fishing is by using electricity to electrocute the fish in the water. This will also disable the movement of other fish and animals in the area. Common sources of electricity for this type of fishing include dry-cell batteries or generators. While cyanide fishing is a prohibited act of fishing method, other chemicals may be prohibited

to incapacitate other predators that might be peripatetic in the area. However, disproportionate usage of it may lead to being detained by the local authorities.

Figure 2.6: A diver spouting cyanide upon the coral reefs in order for the fishes to get outside of their habitat. (Source: thescienceexplorer.com)

Illegal Fishing Laws and Regulations in the Philippines

According to the website of the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR), the forerunner of the laws and regulations of the Philippines in the field of aquaculture is the Philippine Fisheries Code of 1998 or the Republic Act 8550. Pursuant to this law are the implementing rules and regulations of the law, which upholds the following sections that state the bounds of fishing in the Philippines:

- **SEC. 5. Use of Philippine Waters** - The use and exploitation of the fishery and aquatic resources in Philippine waters shall be reserved exclusively to Filipinos: Provided, however, that research and survey activities may be allowed under strict regulations, for purely research, scientific, technological and educational purposes that would also benefit Filipino citizens.
- **SEC. 7. Access to Fishery Resources** - The Department shall issue such number of licenses and permits for the conduct of fishery activities subject to the limits of the MSY of the resource as determined by scientific studies or best available evidence. Preference shall be given to resource users in the local communities adjacent or nearest to the municipal waters.

- **SEC. 8. Catch Ceiling Limitations** - The Secretary may prescribe limitations or quota on the total quantity of fish captured, for a specified period of time and specified area based on the best available evidence. Such a catch ceiling may be imposed per species of fish whenever necessary and practicable: Provided, however, that in municipal waters and fishery management areas, and waters under the jurisdiction of special agencies, catch ceilings may be established upon the concurrence and approval or recommendation of such special agency and the concerned LGU in consultation with the FARMC for conservation or ecological purposes.
- **SEC. 9. Establishment of Closed Season** - The Secretary may declare, through public notice in at least two (2) newspapers of general circulation or in public service announcements, whichever is applicable, at least (5) days before the declaration, a closed season in any or all Philippine waters outside the boundary of municipal waters and in bays, for conservation and ecological purposes. The Secretary may include waters under the jurisdiction of special agencies, municipal waters and bays, and/or other areas reserved for the use of the municipal fisherfolk in the areas to be covered by closed season: Provided, however, That this shall be done only upon the concurrence and approval or recommendation of such special agency and the concerned LGU and FARMC: Provided, further, That in municipal waters, fishery management areas and other areas reserved for the use of the municipal fisherfolk, closed season may be established by the concerned LGU in consultation with the FARMC for conservation or ecological purposes. The FARMCs may also recommend the establishment of closed seasons in municipal waters, fisheries management and other areas reserved for the use of municipal fisherfolk.
- **SEC. 11. Protection of Rare, Threatened and Endangered Species** - The Department shall declare closed seasons and take conservation and rehabilitation measures for rare, threatened and endangered species, as it may determine, and shall ban the fishing and/or taking of rare, threatened and/or endangered species, including their eggs / offspring as identified by existing laws in concurrence with concerned government agencies.
- **SEC. 14. Monitoring, Control and Surveillance of Philippine Waters** - A monitoring, control and surveillance system shall be established by the Department in coordination with LGUs, FARMCs, the private sector and other agencies concerned to ensure that the fisheries and aquatic resources in Philippine waters are judiciously and wisely utilized and managed on a sustainable basis and conserved for the benefit and enjoyment exclusively of Filipino citizens.
- **SEC. 15. Auxiliary Invoices** - All fish and fishery products must have an auxiliary invoice to be issued by the LGUs or their duly authorized representatives prior to their transport from their point of origin to their point of destination in the Philippines and/or export purposes upon payment of a fee to be determined by the LGUs to defray administrative costs therefor.
- **SEC. 16. Jurisdiction of Municipal / City Governments** - The municipal / city government shall have jurisdiction over municipal waters as defined in this Code. The municipal / city government, in consultation with the FARMC shall be responsible for the management, conservation, development, protection, utilization, and disposition of all fish and fishery/aquatic resources within their respective municipal waters. The municipal/city government may, in consultation with the FARMC, enact appropriate ordinances for this purpose and in accordance with the National Fisheries Policy. The ordinances enacted by the municipality and component city shall be reviewed pursuant to Republic Act No. 7160 by the *sanggunian* of the province which has jurisdiction over the same. The LGUs shall also enforce all fishery laws, rules and regulations as well as valid fishery ordinances enacted by the municipality/city council. The management of contiguous fishery resources such as bays which straddle several municipalities, cities or provinces, shall be done in an integrated manner, and shall not be based on political subdivisions of municipal waters in order to facilitate their management as single resource systems. The LGUs which share or border such resources may group themselves and coordinate with each other to achieve the objectives of integrated fishery resource management. The Integrated Fisheries and Aquatic Resources Management Councils (IFARMCs) established under Section 76 of this Code shall serve as the venues for close collaboration among LGUs in the management of contiguous resources.

- **SEC. 17. Grant of Fishing Privileges in Municipal Waters** - The duly registered fisherfolk organizations/cooperatives shall have preference in the grant of fishery rights by the Municipal/City Council pursuant to Section 149 of the Local Government Code: Provided, That in areas where there are special agencies or offices vested with jurisdiction over municipal waters by virtue of special laws creating these agencies such as, but not limited to, the Laguna Lake Development Authority and the Palawan Council for Sustainable Development, said offices and agencies shall continue to grant permits for proper management and implementation of the aforementioned structures.
- **SEC. 18. Users of Municipal Waters** - All fishery activities in municipal waters, as defined in this Code, shall be utilized by municipal fisherfolk and their cooperatives/organizations who are listed as such in the registry of municipal fisherfolk. The municipal or city government, however, may, through its local chief executive and acting pursuant to an appropriate ordinance, authorize or permit small and medium commercial fishing vessels to operate within the ten point one (10.1) to fifteen (15) kilometer area from the shoreline in municipal waters as defined herein, provided, that all the following are met: a. no commercial fishing in municipal waters with depth less than seven (7) fathoms as certified by the appropriate agency; b. fishing activities utilizing methods and gears that are determined to be consistent with national policies set by the Department; c. prior consultation, through public hearing, with the M/CFARMC has been conducted; and d. the applicant vessel as well as the shipowner, employer, captain and crew have been certified by the appropriate agency as not having violated this Code, environmental laws and related laws.
- **SEC. 19. Registry of Municipal Fisherfolk** - The LGU shall maintain a registry of municipal fisherfolk, who are fishing or may desire to fish in municipal waters for the purpose of determining priorities among them, of limiting entry into the municipal waters, and of monitoring fishing activities and/or other related purposes: Provided, That the FARMC shall submit to the LGU the list of priorities for its consideration. Such list or registry shall be updated annually or as may be necessary, and shall be posted in barangay halls or other strategic locations where it shall be open to public inspection, for the purpose of validating the correctness and completeness of the list. The LGU, in consultation with the FARMCs, shall formulate the necessary mechanisms for inclusion or exclusion procedures that shall be most beneficial to the resident municipal fisherfolk. The FARMCs may likewise recommend such mechanisms. The LGUs shall also maintain a registry of municipal fishing vessels by type of gear and other boat particulars with the assistance of the FARMC.
- **SEC. 23. Limited Entry Into Overfished Areas** - Whenever it is determined by the LGUS and the Department that a municipal water is overfished based on available data or information or in danger of being overfished, and that there is a need to regenerate the fishery resources in that water, the LGU shall prohibit or limit fishery activities in the said waters.
- **SEC. 26. Commercial Fishing Vessel License and Other Licenses** - No person shall operate a commercial fishing vessel, pearl fishing vessel or fishing vessel for scientific, research or educational purposes, or engage in any fishery activity, or seek employment as a fishworker or pearl driver without first securing a license from the Department, the period of which shall be prescribed by the Department: Provided, That no such license shall be required of a fishing vessel engaged in scientific research or educational purposes within Philippine waters and pursuant to an international agreement of which the Philippines is a signatory and which agreement defines the status, privileges and obligations of said vessel and its crew and the non-Filipino officials of the international agency under which vessel operates: Provided further, That members of the crew of a fishing vessel used for commercial fishing except the duly licensed and/or authorized patrons, marine engineers, radio operators and cooks shall be considered as fisherfolk: Provided furthermore, That all skippers/master fishers shall be required to undertake an orientation training on detection of fish caught by illegal means before they can be issued their fishworker licenses: Provided finally, That the large commercial fishing vessel license herein authorized to be granted shall allow the licensee to operate only in Philippine waters seven (7) or more fathoms deep, the depth to be certified by the NAMRIA, and subject to the conditions that may be stated therein and the rules and regulations that may be promulgated by the Department.

- **SEC. 27. Persons Eligible for Commercial Fishing Vessel License** - No commercial fishing vessel license shall be issued except to citizens of the Philippines, partnership or to associations, cooperatives or corporations duly registered in the Philippines at least sixty percent (60%) of the capital stock of which is owned by Filipino citizens. No person to whom a license has been issued shall sell, transfer or assign, directly or indirectly, his stock or interest therein to any person not qualified to hold a license. Any such transfer, sale or assignment shall be null and void and shall not be registered in the books of the association, cooperative or corporation. For purposes of commercial fishing, fishing vessel owned by citizens of the Philippines, partnerships, corporations, cooperatives or associations qualified under this section shall secure Certificates of Philippine Registry and such other documents as are necessary for fishing operations from the concerned agencies: Provided, That the commercial fishing vessel license shall be valid for a period to be determined by the Department.
- **SEC. 28. Commercial Fishing Vessel Registration** - The registration, documentation, inspection and manning of the operation of all types of fishing vessels plying Philippine waters shall be in accordance with existing laws, rules and regulations.
- **SEC 29. Registration and Licensing of Fishing Gears Used in Commercial Fishing** - Before a commercial fishing holding a commercial fishing vessel license may begin fishing operations in Philippine waters, the fishing it will utilize in fishing shall be registered and a license granted therefore. The Department shall promulgate guidelines to implement this provision within sixty (60%) days from approval of this Code.
- **SEC. 30. Renewal of Commercial Boats License** - The commercial fishing boat license shall be renewed every three (3) years. The owner/operator of a fishing vessel has a period of sixty (60) days prior to the expiration of the license within which to renew the same.
- **SEC. 31. Report of Transfer of Ownership** - The owner/operator of a registered fishing vessel shall notify the Department in writing of the transfer of the ownership of the vessel with a copy of such document within ten (10) days after its transfer to another person.
- **SEC. 68. Development of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources in Municipal Waters and Bays** - Fisherfolk and their organizations residing within the geographical jurisdiction of the barangays, municipalities or cities with the concerned LGUs shall develop the fishery/aquatic resources in municipal waters and bays.
- **SEC. 69. Creation of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources Management Councils (FARMCs)** - FARMCs shall be established in the national level and in all municipalities/cities abutting municipal waters as defined by this code. The FARMCs shall be formed by fisherfolk organizations/cooperatives and NGOs in the locality and be assisted by the LGUs and other government entities. Before organizing FARMCs, the LGUs, NGOs, fisherfolk, and other concerned POs shall undergo consultation and orientation on the formation of FARMCs.
- **SEC. 86. Unauthorized Fishing or Engaging in other Unauthorized Fisheries Activities** - No person shall exploit, occupy, produce, breed, culture, capture or gather fish, fry or fingerlings of any fishery species or fishery products, or engage in any fishery activity in Philippine waters without a license, lease or permit. Discovery of any person in an area where he has no permit or registration papers for a fishing vessel shall constitute a prima facie presumption that the person and/or vessel is engaged in unauthorized fishing: Provided, that fishing for daily food sustenance or for leisure which is not for commercial, occupation or livelihood purposes may be allowed. It shall be unlawful for any commercial fishing vessel to fish in bays and in such other fishery management areas which may hereinafter be declared as over-exploited. Any commercial fishing boat captain or the three (3) highest officers of the boat who commit any of the above prohibited acts upon conviction shall be punished by a fine equivalent to the value of catch or Ten thousand pesos (P10,000.00) whichever is higher, and imprisonment of six (6) months, confiscation of catch and fishing gears, and automatic revocation of license. It shall be unlawful for any person not listed in the registry of municipal fisherfolk to engage in any commercial fishing activity in municipal waters. Any municipal fisherfolk who commits such violation shall be punished by confiscation of catch and a fine of Five hundred pesos (P500.00).

- **SEC. 87. Poaching in Philippine Waters** - It shall be unlawful for any foreign person, corporation or entity to fish or operate any fishing vessel in Philippine waters. The entry of any foreign fishing vessel in Philippine waters shall constitute a prima facie evidence that the vessel is engaged in fishing in Philippine waters. Violation of the above shall be punished by a fine of One Hundred Thousand U.S. Dollars (US \$100,000.00), in addition to the confiscation of its catch, fishing equipment and fishing vessel: Provided, That the Department is empowered to impose an administrative fine of not less than Fifty Thousand U.S. Dollars (US \$50,000.00) but not more than Two Hundred Thousand U.S. Dollars (US \$200,000.00) or its equivalent in the Philippine Currency.
- **SEC. 88. Fishing Through Explosives, Noxious or Poisonous Substance, and/or Electricity** - [1] It shall be unlawful for any person to catch, take or gather or cause to be caught, taken or gathered, fish or any fishery species in Philippine waters with the use of electricity, explosives, noxious or poisonous substances such as sodium cyanide in the Philippine fishery areas, which will kill, stupefy, disable or render unconscious fish or fishery species: Provided, That the Department, subject to such safeguards and conditions deemed necessary and endorsement from the concerned LGUs may allow, for research, educational or scientific purposes only, the use of electricity, poisonous or noxious substances to catch, take or gather fish or fishery species: Provide, further, That the use of poisonous or noxious substances to eradicate predators in fishponds in accordance with accepted scientific practices and without causing adverse environmental impact in neighboring waters and grounds shall not be construed as illegal fishing. It will likewise be unlawful for any person, corporation or entity to possess, deal in, sell or in any manner dispose of, any fish or fishery species which have been illegally caught, taken or gathered. The discovery of dynamite, other explosives and chemical compounds which contain combustible elements, or noxious or poisonous substance, or equipment or device for electro-fishing in any fishing vessel or in the possession of any fisherfolk, operator, fishing boat official or fishworker shall constitute a prima facie evidence, that the same was used for fishing in violation of this Code. The discovery in any fishing vessel of fish caught or killed with the use of explosive, noxious or poisonous substances or by electricity shall constitute prima facie evidence that the fisherfolk, operator, boat official or fishworker is fishing with the use thereof. [2] Mere possession of explosive, noxious or poisonous substances or electrofishing devices for illegal fishing shall be punishable by imprisonment ranging from six (6) months to two (2) years. [3] Actual use of explosives, noxious or poisonous substances or electrofishing devices for illegal fishing shall be punishable by imprisonment ranging from five (5) years to ten (10) years without prejudice to the filing of separate criminal cases when the use of the same result to physical injury or loss of human life. [4] Dealing in, selling, or in any manner disposing of, for profit, illegally caught / gathered fisheries species shall be punished by imprisonment ranging from six (6) months to two (2) years. [5] In all cases enumerated above, the explosives, noxious or poisonous substances and/or electrical devices, as well as the fishing vessels, fishing equipment and catch shall be forfeited. SEC. 89. Use of Fine Mesh Net - It shall be unlawful to engage in fishing using nets with mesh smaller than that with which may be fixed by the Department: Provided, That the prohibition on the use of fine mesh net shall not apply to the gathering of fry, glass eels, elvers, *tabios*, and *alamang* and such species which by their nature are small but already mature to be identified in the implementing rules and regulations by the Department. Violation of the above shall subject the offender to a fine from Two thousand pesos (P2,000.00) to Twenty thousand pesos (P20,000.00) or imprisonment from six (6) months to two (2) years or both such fine and imprisonment at the discretion of the court: Provided, That if the offense is committed by a commercial fishing vessel, the boat captain and the master fisherman shall also be subject to the penalties herein: Provided, further, That the owner/operator of the commercial fishing vessel who violates this provision shall be subjected to the same penalties provided herein: Provided, finally, That the Department is hereby empowered to impose upon the offender an administrative fine and/or cancel his permit or license or both.
- **SEC. 90. Use of Active Gear in the Municipal Waters and Bays and Other Fishery Management Areas** - It shall be unlawful to engage in fishing in municipal waters and in all bays as well as other fishery management areas using active fishing gears as defined in this Code.

- **SEC. 91. Ban on Coral Exploitation and Exportation** - It shall be unlawful for any person or corporation to gather, possess, sell or export ordinary precious and semi-precious corals, whether raw or in processed form, except for scientific or research purposes. Violations of this provision shall be punished by imprisonment from six (6) months to two (2) years and a fine from Two thousand pesos (P2,000.00) to Twenty thousand pesos (P20,000.00), or both such fine and imprisonment, at the discretion of the court, and forfeiture of the subject corals, including the vessel and its proper disposition. The confiscated corals shall either be returned to the sea or donated to schools and museums for educational or scientific purposes or disposed through other means.
- **SEC. 92. Ban on Muro-Ami, Other Methods and Gear Destructive to Coral Reefs and Other Marine Habitat** - It shall be unlawful for any person, natural or juridical, to fish with gear method that destroys coral reefs, seagrass beds, and other fishery marine life habitat as may be determined by the Department. "Muro-Ami" and any of its variation, and such similar gear and methods that require diving, other physical or mechanical acts to pound the coral reefs and other habitat to entrap, gather or catch fish and other fishery species are also prohibited. The operator, boat captain, master fisherman, and recruiter or organizer of fishworkers who violate this provision shall suffer a penalty of two (2) years to ten (10) years imprisonment and a fine of not less than One hundred thousand pesos (P100,000.00) to Five hundred thousand pesos (P500,000.00) or both such fine and imprisonment, at the discretion of the court. The catch and gear used shall be confiscated. It shall likewise be unlawful for any person or corporation to gather, sell or export white sand, silica, pebbles and any other substances which make up any marine habitat. The person or corporation who violates this provision shall suffer a penalty of two (2) years to ten (10) years imprisonment and a fine of not less than One hundred thousand pesos (P100,000.00) to Five hundred thousand pesos (P500,000.00) or both such fine and imprisonment, at the discretion of the court. The substance taken from its marine habitat shall be confiscated.
- **SEC. 93. Illegal Use of Superlights** - It shall be unlawful to engage in fishing with the use of superlights in municipal waters or in violation of the rules and regulations which may be promulgated by the Department on the use of superlights outside municipal waters. Violations of this provision shall be punished by imprisonment from six (6) months to two (2) years or a fine of Five thousand pesos (P5,000.00) per superlight, or both such fine and imprisonment at the discretion of the courts. The superlight, fishing gears and vessel shall be confiscated.
- **SEC. 94. Conversion of Mangroves** - It shall be unlawful for any person to convert mangroves into fishponds or for any other purposes. Violation of the provision of this section shall be punished by imprisonment of six (6) years and one (1) day to twelve (12) years and/or a fine of Eighty thousand pesos (P80,000.00): Provided, that if the area requires rehabilitation or restoration as determined by the court, the offender should also be required to restore or compensate for the restoration of the damage.
- **SEC. 95. Fishing in Overfished Area and During Closed Season** - It shall be unlawful to fish in overfished area and during closed season. Violation of the provision of this section shall be punished by imprisonment of six (6) months and one (1) day to six (6) years and/or fine of Six thousand pesos (P6,000.00) and by forfeiture of the catch and cancellation of fishing permit or license.
- **SEC. 96. Fishing in Fishery Reserves, Refuge and Sanctuaries** - It shall be unlawful to fish in fishery areas declared by the Department as fishery reserves, refuge and sanctuaries. Violation of the provision of this section shall be punished by imprisonment of two (2) years to six (6) years and/or fine of Two thousand pesos (P2,000.00) to Twenty thousand pesos (P20,000.00) and by forfeiture of the catch and the cancellation of fishing permit or license.
- **SEC. 97. Fishing or Taking of Rare, Threatened or Endangered Species** - It shall be unlawful to fish or take rare, threatened or endangered species as listed in the CITES and as determined by the Department. Violation of the provision of this section shall be punished by imprisonment of twelve (12) years to twenty (20) years and/or a fine of One hundred and twenty thousand pesos (P120,000.00) and forfeiture of the catch, and the cancellation of fishing permit.
- **SEC. 98. Capture of Sabalo and Other Breeders / Spawners** - It shall be unlawful for any person to catch, gather, capture or possess mature milkfish or "sabalo" and such other breeders or spawners of other fishery species as may be determined by the Department: Provided, that catching of *sabalo* and

other breeders/spawners for local breeding purposes or scientific or research purposes may be allowed subject to guidelines to be promulgated by the Department. Violation of the provision of this section shall be punished by imprisonment of six (6) months and one (1) day to eight (8) years and/or a fine of Eighty Thousand Pesos (P80,000.00) and forfeiture of the catch, and fishing equipment used and revocation of license.

- **SEC. 99. Exportation of Breeders, Spawners, Eggs or Fry** - Exportation of breeders, spawners, eggs or fry as prohibited in this Code shall be punished by imprisonment of eight (8) years, confiscation of the same or a fine equivalent to double the value of the same, and revocation of the fishing and/or export license/permit.
- **SEC. 100. Importation or Exportation of Fish or Fishery Species** - Any importation or exportation of fish or fisheries species in violation of this Code shall be punished by eight (8) years of imprisonment, a fine of Eighty Thousand Pesos (P80,000.00) and destruction of live fishery species or forfeiture of non-live fishery species in favor of the department for its proper disposition: Provided, That violator of this provision shall be banned from being members or stock holders of companies currently engaged in fisheries or companies to be created in the future, the guidelines for which shall be promulgated by the Department.
- **SEC. 101. Violation of Catch Ceilings** - It shall be unlawful for any person to fish in violation of catch ceilings as determined by the Department. Violation of the provision of this section shall be punished by imprisonment of six (6) months and one (1) day to six (6) years and/or a fine of Fifty Thousand Pesos (P50,000.00) and forfeiture of the catch, and fishing equipment used and revocation of license.
- **SEC. 102. Aquatic Pollution** - Aquatic pollution, as defined in this Code shall be unlawful. Violation of the provision of this section shall be punished by imprisonment of six (6) years and one (1) day to twelve (12) years and/or a fine of Eighty thousand pesos (P80,000.00) plus an additional fine of Eight thousand pesos (P8,000.00) per day until such violation ceases and the fines paid.
- **SEC. 103. Other Violations** - The following fisheries activities shall also be considered as a violation of this Code: [1] Failure to Comply with Minimum Safety Standards. - The owner and captain of a commercial fishing vessel engaged in fishing who, upon demand by proper authorities, fails to exhibit or show proof of compliance with the safety standards provided in this Code, shall be immediately prevented from continuing with his fishing activity and escorted to the nearest port or landing point. The license to operate the commercial fishing vessel shall be suspended until the safety standard has been complied with. [2] Failure to Conduct a Yearly Report on all Fishponds, Fish Pens and Fish Cages. - The FLA of the holder who fails to render a yearly report shall be immediately canceled: Provided, that if the offender be the owner of the fishpond, fish pen or fish cage, he shall be subjected to the following penalties: (1) first offense, a fine of Five hundred pesos (P500.00) per unreported hectare; (2) subsequent offenses, a fine of One thousand pesos (P1,000.00) per unreported hectare. [3] Gathering and Marketing of Shell Fishes. - It shall be unlawful for any person to take, sell, transfer, or have in possession for any purpose any shell fish which is sexually mature or below the minimum size or above the maximum quantities prescribed for the particular species. [4] Obstruction to Navigation or Flow and Ebb of Tide in any Stream, River, Lake or Bay. - It shall be unlawful for any person who causes obstruction to navigation or flow of ebb of tide. [5] Construction and Operation of Fish Corals/Traps, Fish Pens and Fish Cages. - It shall be unlawful to construct and operate fish corals/traps, fish pens and fish cages without a license/permit.
- **SEC. 104. Commercial Fishing Vessel Operators Employing Unlicensed Fisherfolk or Fishworker or Crew** - The owner / operator of a commercial fishing vessel employing unlicensed fisherfolk or fishworker shall be fined Five hundred pesos (P500.00) each for every month that the same has been employed and / or One thousand pesos (P1,000.00) for every month for each unlicensed crew member who has been employed.
- **SEC. 105. Obstruction of Defined Migration Paths** - Obstruction of any defined migration paths of anadromous, catadromous and other migratory species, in areas including, but not limited to river mouths and estuaries within a distance determined by the concerned FARMCs shall be punished by imprisonment of seven (7) years to twelve (12) years or a fine from Fifty thousand pesos (P50,000.00)

to One hundred thousand pesos (P100,000.00) or both imprisonment and fine at the discretion of the court, and cancellation of permit/license, if any, and dismantling of obstruction shall be at his own expense and confiscation of same.

- **SEC. 106. Obstruction to Fishery Law Enforcement Officer** - The boat owner, master or operator or any person acting on his behalf of any fishing vessel who evades, obstructs or hinder any fishery law enforcement officer of the Department to perform his duty, shall be fined Ten thousand pesos (P10,000.00). In addition, the registration, permit and/or license of the vessel including the license of the master fisherman shall be canceled.
- **SEC.125. Strengthening Prosecution and Conviction of Violators of Fishery Laws** - The Department of Justice (DOJ) shall embark on a program to strengthen the prosecution and conviction aspects of fishery law enforcement through augmentation of the current complement of state prosecutors and through their continuous training and reorientation on fishery laws, rules and regulations.

Alongside with RA 8550, the field of fisheries regulations is also backed up by the Agriculture and Fisheries Modernization Act of 1997 (RA 8435), Presidential Decree No. 704, and the amendment of RA 8550, Republic Act No. 10654.

Local and International Issues of Illegal Fishing in the Philippines

Locally, there are many cases of illegal fishing around the Philippines. Such examples include a case that was described in the news.

GMA News has reported in December 2013 under its evening news show, 24 Oras, has reported that a large portion of coral reefs are now obliterated due to the effects of blast fishing.

One News PH has reported in February 2019, that due to illegal fishing practices, the Department of Agriculture (DA) has revealed that the Philippines is losing trillions of pesos in revenue. Adding to this report, a study that is published by Oceana Philippines states that unlawful fishing activities is most evident in areas in Mindanao and MIMAROPA.

Eagle News in September 2019 has reported that seven fishing vessels have been impounded by the Oroquieta City coast guard as a part of their anti-illegal fishing operation in the city.

A report in the news show QRT (Quick Response Team) by GMA News TV (now known as GTV) on October 2019 has shown three men being nabbed by the Philippine National Police in the waters of Manila Bay.

In Alabel, Sarangani, 33 fishworkers were arrested upon the unauthorized use of fine mesh nets in fishing (PNA, 2019). Under the Republic Act of 8550 and the amended version, Republic Act 10654, the use of these nets is illegal because they do not let younger fish to escape if they ever get caught and repopulate the population of the fishes.

Two fishermen were arrested by the 102nd Maritime Police for illegal fishing in the waters that are under the territories of Pangasinan and Ilocos Norte on January 2020. Another case of illegal fishing was brought up by Eagle News in March 2020, where seven people have been apprehended in Matnog, Sorsogon due to the unsolicited use of air compressor in their fishing activities.

Figure 2.7: A news clip showing fishermen being apprehended after being caught in the act of illegal fishing. (Source: Eagle News)

According to Mongabay (2020), data according to satellites indicate an increase in commercial fishing vessels operating in waters within 15 kilometers (9 miles) of the Philippine coast, which is off limits for fishing according to the implementations of Republic Act 10654.

On June 2020, a report in DZMM Teleradyo under the segment of Gerry Baja's Garantisadong Balita stated that eight men were arrested for the usage of blast fishing on the waters of Manila Bay. TV% under its primetime show Aksyon, reported that 24 fishermen have been arrested for illegal fishing activities in the province of Bulacan due to the use of *sudsud* or motorized pushnets.

In August 2020, it is reported that the Philippines protested against the rash decision of the Chinese Navy in confiscating the contents of the *payaos* of Filipino fishermen that only want to fish in the area o Scarborough Shoal. The Scarborough Shoal, or locally known as the Panatag Shoal or Bajo de Masinloc, is one of the areas that are under the responsibility of the Philippine government that are being claimed by China along with the economic zones of Vietnam, Taiwan, Malaysia, and Brunei Darussalam.

Figure 2.8: An online news article showing the illegal actions of China in what they call their territories even if they are not. (Source: Cable News Network)

Despite being invalidated by the Permanent Court of Arbitration of the United Nations in The Hague, Netherlands in July 2016, China still persists in an old historical map that has no real significance rather than a trading map that were used during the

olden times – a proof of their culture greatly influenced by communism to save their shameful faces on behalf of their ancestors.

In March 2021, the Philippine has reiterated that the People's Republic of China recall more than 200 Chinese boats it said had been spotted at a disputed reef claimed by both Manila and Beijing, unfolding their presence as a "clear provocative action" where administration officials released pictures of Chinese vessels secured at the boomerang-shaped Whitsun Reef, which Manila calls the Julian Felipe Reef, close to Palawan in the South China Sea on March 7.

Karagatan Patrol

The public Facebook group, Karagatan Patrol, was created by Oceana Philippines and supported by the League of Municipalities of the Philippines on January 13, 2019, which stages up a platform for authorities and civilians of different places in the Philippines to report, share, and discuss about the status of illegal fishing in municipal waters in the country. Citizens that are active on Facebook are encouraged to join the campaign to restore Philippine oceans, enforce the ban on commercial fishing vessels inside municipal waters, and defend the livelihood of fisherfolk.

Along with that, the group also informs the public of news, leads, or information that Oceana Philippines has provided to law enforcement agencies - local government units, Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR), the Philippine National Police (PNP), PNP Maritime Group (PNP Bantay Dagat), Philippine Coast Guard, Philippine Navy, and the National Coast Watch Center.

Figure 2.9 - 2.11: The cover photo, landing webpage of the Facebook group of Karagatan Patrol, and the media that are shared within the group. (Sources: Alan Po, Marc Andrie Bermundo)

Karagathon and Winning Projects

As said in the introduction, the Karagathon: A Hackathon to Combat Illegal Fishing in the Philippines, is implemented with the hopes of searching the most innovative ideas that can help fight illegal fishing in the Philippine municipal waters. Alongside with complementing with the updates of Karagatan Patrol, a Facebook group where authorities and private people and organizations including Oceana Philippines can post about activities and updates of illegal fishing and municipal coast guard activities.

Figure 2.12 - 2.15: The Slack channels that were used during the Karagathon competition as well as the pictures used for the awarding ceremony.
(Sources: Marc Andrie Bermundo)

In the website of Karagatan Patrol, the problem statement for this contest is stated as follows:

The Philippines' maritime domain, consisting of municipal waters, territorial/internal waters and exclusive economic zone, is seven (7) times larger than its terrestrial area. This vast expanse of marine waters holds the most valuable source of marine-based food products that sustains the protein requirements of most Filipinos. Inherent to this large area of marine waters is the effective enforcement of Philippine laws such as the Fisheries Code (RA 8550) as amended by RA 10654

The capacity to track and detect violations is an important element in law enforcement. Thus, more effective means of detection have to be employed by our national and local enforcement agencies in our waters.

Requiring transparency in the actions and behavior of commercial fishing vessels through the installation of vessel monitoring technology in each boat is an important feature of RA 10564. Tracking movements of the commercial fishing vessels is now done using space-based technologies such as what Global Fishing Watch is availing and these are freely accessible and may provide a cost-effective means of enforcement.

The Karagatan Patrol uses data from Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS), a satellite sensor that can detect fishing boats that employ lights to attract fish at night.

Under our laws, specifically the Local Government Code (RA 7160) and the Fisheries Code (RA 8550 as amended by RA 10654), local government units from coastal municipalities and cities have the mandate to protect the rights of fisherfolks in the preferential use of the municipal waters. Municipal waters are marine waters fifteen (15) kilometers from the coastline and these areas are the most productive part of the seas attracting all sorts of fishing activities including those that are prohibited under the law such as fishing by commercial fishing vessels 3.1 gross tons and above. Illegal commercial fishing is among the major threats in the municipal waters apart from overfishing, habitat destruction, pollution and coastal development.

Establishing physical boundaries in these municipal waters is a challenge unless technology is used as a tool (GPS, etc.) to establish jurisdiction when a violation is committed (i.e. commercial fishing boats fishing or encroaching municipal waters under the jurisdiction of a particular local government)

To the consternation of municipal fisherfolk, and as Karagatan Patrol subscribers have shared, commercial fishing boats still enter the 15-kilometer municipal waters and other prohibited zones regularly without the local government units that have jurisdiction knowing it is occurring or, in other cases, not even taking action to implement fisheries laws. While there is a technology that detects lights of fishing vessels, it does not cover boats turning off their lights and those that operate at day time. The government will be installing trackers on all the commercial fishing boats soon but there will always be boats that may not comply or turn off their trackers when they fish in prohibited zones.

Fisheries law enforcers or anyone observing commercial fishing activity in the municipal waters has to establish that these activities are within the prohibited zone before responding considering that enforcement entails costs. But from afar they have difficulty in identifying the boat, including the size, fishing gears and other information about the boat.

There are at least 5 laws that govern commercial fishing in the Philippines, among these are: Fisheries Code as amended by RA 10654, labor law, anti-trafficking law, domestic shipping law and merchant marine law. There are at least 30 agencies tasked to enforce them.

While the Bureau of Fisheries has adjudicators that are tasked to investigate and penalize administratively violations and render timely decisions but they, and the prosecutors and judges, have to be equipped with readily accessible facts and circumstances of the case to render fair judgement.

Lastly, due to the current state of enforcement in the Philippines, it is common for fishing vessels to commit multiple violations in the same area or in other areas. Under the amended Fisheries Code of the Philippines, a fishing vessel committing multiple violations can be sanctioned through cancellation or suspension

of their fishing permit. But without a repository or system for tracking and monitoring violations of fishing vessels in various jurisdiction, this sanction might remain on paper and will not be a deterrence to comply with the law.

About Karagathon

Karagathon or 'Karagatan' hackathon is a codefest for finding innovative mechanisms and technology-based avenue in addressing the burgeoning challenges haunting our seas to achieve sustainable fisheries and healthy seas for all Filipinos. Karagathon is also envisioned to complement and enhance the existing initiative between [OCEANA](#) and [the League of Municipalities of the Philippines](#), the '[Karagatan Patrol online platform](#)' for reporting illegal fishing and the '[Karagatan Patrol web application](#)' for Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite - Boat Detection.

The 1st KARAGATHON will focus on the technology-based innovations to address the challenges in fully implementing fisheries and related laws that directly affect the health and resiliency of our seas and our fisheries.

Figure 2.7: The description panel of the Karagathon competition alongside with the logo of the Karagathon on the right. (Source: karagatanpatrol.org)

The winners for the first ever Karagathon are Parrotfish.net, Hydraean, and Oceans 13 (Mod 7).

Figure 2.8: The logos of the three Karagathon winners. (Source: Oceana Philippines)

The champion for the first Karagathon, ParrotFish.net, has a project called ParrotFish Seamate, a portable battery-operated fishing boat tracker and transceiver that forms part of a smart wireless network which serves as smart buoys equipped with sound detection technology and satellite systems to identify entries of unauthorized fishing vessels in municipal waters. In combination with the portable Seamate comes with the Seamaster buoys that are equipped with the Sealight lighting system for the said buoys. Information from their products is then communicated to the authorities. The ParrotFish team said that it has been successfully pilot tested in El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental.

The second-place winner, Hydraean, has a solution called Seantinel, an open internet-of-things (IoT) platform will real-time data processing that can be used to report illegal fishing activities without the need of reliance to expensive equipment. The Seantinel system can be scaled up by upgrading the connections in their IoT system.

Figure 2.9: The winners of the first Karagathon competition.
(Source: Oceana Philippines)

The third placer, Ocean's 13 (Mod 7) proposes the BaTMon (Banca Tracking and Monitoring System). The system that they've made has four components. The BaT-Mobile, an application on mobile phones that tracks the movements of minor boats of *bancas*, BaT-dBase, a database system that stores for the three other components, the BaT-Web, a web-based platform for exhibiting the location of the bancas, and the BaT-CAM, a postponement of the BaT-Web that uses data for analytics and creates graphs for the use of the public community and academics.

METHODOLOGY

Sensor Buoy Systems

Utilizing sensors in buoys has been long been implemented and explored by many academics. Most of the sensors that are being used by researchers and the scientific community are Arduino-based microcontrollers. Arduino microcontrollers are manufactured under the Arduino brand, an open-source platform used for the construction electronics projects. Arduino consists of both a physical programmable circuit board, also known as a microcontroller, and a piece of software, called the IDE or Integrated Development Environment that runs on computers to write and upload code that is written into the microcontroller.

As distinguished in the website of Spark Fun (2013), the platform turned out to be popular with people that are just starting out with electronics as the Arduino does not need a separate piece of hardware (called a programmer) in order to load new code onto the board instead, it only lets users to simply use a USB cable. Additionally, the IDE is set to be routinely used under a simplified version of C++, making it easier to learn to program, along with the compactness that is taken into a simple yet affordable microcontroller.

Furthermore, the Arduino boasts a collection of hardware and software that was designed for artists, designers, hobbyists, hackers, newbies, and anyone interested in creating interactive objects or environments. Using this microcontroller, it interacts with

buttons, LEDs, motors, speakers, GPS units, cameras, the internet, even with phone and TV. This feature along with the other mentioned capabilities of the Arduino microcontroller and software has led to a community of users that contributed code and released instructional materials for varieties of projects.

Figure 3.1: The Arduino webpage. (Source: Arduino CC)

The features of the Arduino hardware and software, has been also used in studies including sensor buoy systems, as with the case of Demetillo et. al. (2019). In their study, they have made a wireless sensor network (WSN) that is appropriate for monitoring characteristics of water in more remote areas without requiring the need for a lot of manpower and instead relying on low-cost equipment. In their output, the buoy system was designed to provide data collection and storage, data dissemination and display, power management, and maintenance interface for administrators for the system.

A virtual control buoy (VCB) concept has been published on Australia by Mullen et. al. (2009) uses autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) that is used in order to have functionalities while inspecting to remote subsea wellheads for the production of natural

gas, which in the paper says that it eliminates the need for expensive long distance control buoys, which are also cheap but have limitations.

Buoy systems for acquiring these types of data were at least common to everyone in the field, since as early as 1975, there has been a journal on control buoys as seen in a paper submitted by Hall et. al. under the data buoy office of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

In another paper by Duran Neira and Hermida (2011), their patented buoy system is a remote-controlled buoy with multiple parameters designed for water sampling analysis under various conditions, an isolated reading and analysis module for checking the characteristics defining the characteristics of the environment, remote-controlled maintenance system for calibrating the buoy using remoted-based technologies and standards, power source systems, and a pre-programmed data monitoring and transmission system.

Similarly in Europe, a paper has been published by Garcia et. al. in 2018 about a multi-faceted floater system that is tucked with sensors and payloads in order to extract information. Their modules also borrow elements from other open-source materials that are available in their region.

Knight et. al. (2020) made a low-cost GNSS buoy tide gauge that is comparable with more expensive GNSS buoys and is also ideal for the procurement of local-scale coastal sea level data. Adding to the efficiency of the data that is gathered, results also indicate the presence of high frequency oscillations in the sea level data caused by coastal geometry and wave-induced disturbance.

Sensor Fusion

Douglas (n.d.) says that sensor fusion is combining two or more data sources in a way that generates a better understanding of the system. The understanding of the data refers to the solution being more stable and consistent over time, more accurate, and more dependable than it would be with a single data source.

In addition, Douglas (n.d.) also gives reasons for sensor fusion, with the main one in the sense that mechanisms need to increase the quality of the data, which means that the data collected from the sensors has less noise, less uncertainty, and fewer deviations. The second reason from the usage of sensor fusion is to increase the reliability of the measurements, and the final reason for using sensor fusion is to approximate certain unmeasured states in a system.

Figure 3.2: The introductory video regarding the betterment of understanding sensor fusion in MATLAB. (Source: MathWorks.com)

While losing a sensor doesn't always mean the sensor failed, this possibly will also signify that the quantity they're gaging into drops out momentarily, which is hard for a researcher to find some uncertainties in the product output. Albeit the system used in Buoyani does not use MATLAB, but instead relying on cheaper systems and controller boards, the buoys in Buoyani would definitely use sensor fusion for the job.

Analysis of Remote Sensing Payloads

Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)

LiDAR, abbreviation for light detection ranging (also known as active laser scanning) is a remote sensing technique that can be used for defining the topological characteristics across a region. As the capabilities of LiDAR directly measures the height and density of vegetation on the ground, it makes it an ideal tool to be used for by scientists studying vegetation over large areas. LiDAR is an active system where it emits light from a rapidly firing laser.

The lights travel to the ground and replicates off the topological structures of the area and relaying it to the system in order for it to be recorded. It also measures the time it takes for emitted light to travel to the ground and back to calculate the distance traveled which can be turned into elevation if the LiDAR is pulsed above ground. These measurements include the global positioning system (GPS) tucked in into the system along with the orientations of the system in three different axes (X, Y, Z) in the sky or in a fixed location. A lot of LiDAR's will have an intensity value that notes the amount of light energy recorded by the sensor.

LiDAR works with the accumulation of light energy, a collection of photons. As photon that make up light moves towards the ground, they hit objects such as branches on a tree. A minimal amount of light bounces off and comes back into the sensor. Some of the light may continue through underground, while some may bounce off again in other structures, making the lights record repetitive recordings.

This energy distribution is the waveform, and the amount of light coming back to become part of waveform recording is the intensity. Detected areas where more photons or more light energy returns to the sensor create peaks in the distribution of energy, these peaks determine an object that was detected by the LiDAR.

Waveforms using LiDAR may be discrete or full. A discrete records individual (discrete) points for the peaks in the waveform curve. This type of LiDAR systems identifies peaks and record a point at each peak location in the waveform curve. These discrete or individual points are called returns. A discrete system may record commonly

up to four returns from each laser pulse, depending on the circumstance. Meanwhile, full waveform LiDAR systems records a distribution of returned light energy. They are more complex but they give more information compared to discrete return LiDAR systems.

Figure 3.3: An example of LiDAR data, with this picture being collected at the Soaproot Saddle site by the National Ecological Observatory Network's Airborne Observation Platform. (Source: National Ecological Observatory Network's Airborne Observation Platform (NEON AOP))

Sound Navigation and Ranging (SONAR)

The term SONAR is the abbreviation for Sound Navigation and Ranging. Scientists primarily use sonar to develop nautical charts, locate underwater hazards to navigation, search for and map objects on the seafloor such as shipwrecks, and map the seafloor itself since using SONAR is helpful for exploring and mapping the ocean because sound waves travel farther in the water than do radar and light waves (NOAA, 2013).

Figure 3.4: An example of a soanr image, from the Soviet Navy minesweeper T-297, formerly the Latvian Virsaitis, which was shipwrecked on 3 December 1941 in the Gulf of Finland. (Source: Wikipedia User, Muinsuskaitseamet)

There are two types of SONAR that is being used, active SONAR's are systems are used primarily to emit an acoustic signal or pulse of sound into the water. When an object is on the way of the SONAR's sound pulse, the sound bounces off the object and returns an "echo" to the transducer. If the transducer is equipped with the ability to receive signals, it measures the strength of the signal. Determining the time between the emission of the sound pulse and its reception can also be done by active SONAR's. in order to identify what is the range and orientation of the object.

Passive SONAR's work by detecting the noise that is emitted by other objects that can be found along the area, which can be used for scientific expeditions which objectives are concentrated on silently "listening" to the ocean. This type of SONAR has the disadvantage of not knowing the range of an object unless used in conjunction with other devices. However, multiple passive SONAR's can be used for the triangulation of an object that has been emitting noises.

Radio Detection and Ranging (RADAR)

RADAR stands for Radio Detection and Ranging System, an electromagnetic system that is being used to perceive location and distance of an object from the point where it is placed. It works by radiating energy into space and monitoring the echo or reflected signal from the objects. It operates in the ultra – high frequencies (UHF) and microwave ranges under ranges of 400 MHz to 40 GHz (Argawal, 2020).

The device works via an electromagnetic sensor that is used to notice, track, locate, and identify different objects at certain distances. RADAR's transmit electromagnetic energy in the direction of targets to observe the echoes and returns from them. The targets of RADAR apparatuses may vary from shipping vessels, airplanes, celestial bodies, automotive vehicles, spacecraft, rain, birds, insects, etc. Other RADAR's may also gather the shape and size of the target objects.

Compared to infrared and optical sensing devices, the RADAR is much more effective in determining faraway targets under problematic conditions regarding climate with precise distances and ranges. RADAR's are also equipped with transmitters that are identified for being a light source for the placed targets. Indispensable components

found in RADAR systems are transmitters, waveguides, antennas, antenna duplexers, and receivers with threshold decisions.

Figure 3.4: An example of a radar device that is used for navigation.
(Source: Wikipedia, Clipper)

When RADAR units are positioned on a ship or plane, they require a similar essential set of components to produce radio signals, transmit them into space and receive them by something, and finally display the information to understand it. RADAR units use magnetrons to generate radio signals which are used through radio. These signals are similar to light signals as they travel at the same speed but their signals are lengthier with less frequencies.

In the electromagnetic spectrum, both the signals like radio and light are made with variable designs of magnetic and electrical energy throughout the air. The magnetron in radar generates microwaves the same as a microwave oven. The main disparity is that the magnetron within radar has to transmit the signals several miles, rather than just small distances, so it is more powerful as well as much larger. Whenever the radio signals have been transmitted, then an antenna functions as a transmitter to transmit them into the air.

Figure 3.5: A long – range RADAR antenna that was used for tracking objects that are in space as well as ballistic missiles found in Kwajalein atoll.
(Source: Wikipedia, Ronald Reagan Ballistic Missile Defense Test Site)

The beveled shape of the RADAR antennas is designed in this way as it focuses the signals into a specified signal, but the RADAR antennas also rotate around so they can notice actions over a huge area. Signals that travel outside from the antenna with 300,000 km per second speed until they strike something and some of them return back to the antenna. Duplexers that are found on RADAR's are used to make the antenna change from side to side in between a transmitter & a receiver (Argawal, 2020).

Analysis of Communication Payloads

LoRaWAN

LoRaWAN is a type of LPWAN network, which stands for Low-power Wide-area Network. LPWAN networks are wireless and have a wide coverage radius, with the main advantage of such networks is low power consumption, and the amount of data transfer in such networks is measured in bytes, but this is enough to transmit the necessary telemetry from the end device to the dispatcher server. The lifetime of these end devices is several years on a single battery and depends on the data transfer schedule (Telemetric Tech, 2020).

Figure 3.6: The LoRaWAN network architecture. (Source: Telemetric Technologies)

Basically, devices with LPWAN connection are typical microcontrollers with minimal power consumption and a wireless network interface. These devices usually communicate with their gateway (base station), which has an IP address for accessing the Internet. This type of technology was developed and supported by the Lora Alliance, which is to be made up of international telecommunications companies and manufacturers, as well as integrators.

The LoRaWAN technology platform can be segmented into two components, the LoRa being the proprietary technology with LoRaWAN radio modulation that uses wireless connectivity to connect between end devices and gateways and the LoRaWAN's access control protocol that uses media access control (MAC) address identification to transmit and manage messages between the LoRaWAN Network Server and the end device.

Kinematic Global Positioning System (GPS)

Real - time kinematic (RTK) positioning developed from the centimeter - level accuracy positioning in real-time based on GPS or GNSS measurements that was developed during the 1990's. The system involves a reference receiver transmitting its raw measurements or observation corrections to a rover receiver via data communication. Data processing that is found at the rover site contains ambiguity resolution of the differenced carrier phase data and coordinate estimation of the rover position. However, a significant drawback of RTK positioning is that the maximum distance between reference and receiver ambiguities. Limitations that are found the RTK positioning is caused by distance - dependent biases such as orbit error, and ionospheric and tropospheric signal refraction. These errors, however, can be accurately modelled using the measurements of an array of GNSS reference stations surrounding the rover site. Thus, RTK positioning is extended from a single base to a multi-base technique (Wanninger, 2018).

The data processing for network RTK positioning consists of three distinct steps. In the first processing step ambiguity fixing is performed in the reference station network. The second processing step correction model coefficients are estimated (Dai et. al., 2001). Numerous techniques have been established to interpolate the distance - dependent biases between reference stations and user receivers. The third processing step is an optimum set of reference observations is computed from the observations of a selected master reference station, the one closest to the rover receiver, and the precise correction models for distance-dependent biases (Wanninger, 2003).

Figure 3.6: The data networking for real time kinematic GPS positioning. (Source: International Association of Geodesy)

Figure 3.7: A diagram of real - time kinematic GPS and receiving stations on ground.
(Source: Pennsylvania State University)

GSM Module

The Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) is a standard developed by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) to describe the protocols for second-generation (2G) digital cellular networks used by mobile devices such as mobile phones and tablets. It was first deployed in Finland in December 1991. By the mid-2010s, it became a global standard for mobile communications achieving over 90% market share, and operating in over 193 countries and territories.

The network structure of GSM is divided into the base station subsystem for control, network and switching subsystem for the networks, GPRS core network for packet internet connections, and operations support system for maintenance.

Structure of a GSM network

Figure 3.8: The structure of a GSM-based network.
(Source: Wikipedia User, Tsaitgaist)

There are various cell sizes in a GSM system such as macro, micro, pico, and umbrella cells. Each cell varies as per the implementation domain. There are five different cell sizes in a GSM network cells. The coverage area of the cells vary according to the implementation environment. The time division multiple access (TDMA) technique relies on assigning different time slots to each user on the same frequency. It can easily adapt to data broadcast and voice communication and can carry 64kbps to 120Mbps of data rate (Argawal, 2020).

Figure 3.9: The circuitries of a GSM Modem. (Source: Elprocus.com)

Altimeter Module

An altimeter measures the height from it in above particular pressure levels. This device compares the pressure of outside static air to the standard pressure of air at sea level (29.92" Hg). Every .1" Hg is equivalent to 100 feet in altitude. The air is denser at sea level than higher grounds, thus the pressure decreases as the altitude increases (Boldmethod.com, 2020).

Figure 3.10: The mechanisms of a typical altimeter. (Source: Boldmethod.com)

Meanwhile, newer altimeters have been integrated into glass cockpits in newer aircrafts, where the readings are generated by an Air Data Computer (ADC), which uses the same static air input to measure altitude. However, the static air never enters a diaphragm the same way it does in a traditional altimeter. This is done by sending digital signals to show the correct output of the altitude that was forecasted. This means that there are also fewer arms that tick unlike the traditional altimeter.

Figure 3.11: An electronic altimeter that is projected into a glass aircraft cockpit. (Source: Boldmethod.com)

Water Quality Module

Assessing the quality of water in a sensor - based data buoy like Buoyani would need a lot of components. The buoy may need to include modules for checking the quality of water, the turbidity, the pH level, and many others.

Looking upon the water quality modules that are openly available to the public by the Hydrologic Engineering Center (HEC) of the United States Army (HEC, 2020), the water quality modules that are made to enhance the capabilities of performing water quality examinations. The set of the modules that were made are temperature simulation modules, constituent simulation modules, and nutrient simulation modules. These modules simulate and examine the necessary components when looking upon conditions in the water.

In the case of this upcoming project however, the project is only limited in a series of payloads that are cheap yet effective in guarding the vicinity surrounding it as well as communicating the status of the area. This will let us create a buoy with a profiling system

that can occur regularly to provide consistent, high quality, streaming of data (Fondriest, 2014).

Figure 3.12: Flow diagram of one of the modules used by the US Army, the Nutrient Simulation Module Mark II or NSMII. (Source: Hydrologic Engineering Center, US Army)

In this project, the Buoyani would first contain a turbidity sensor, a water sensor, and a flow rate sensor. The turbidity sensor will look out if the liquid where the buoy floats in is cloudy or hazy at the moment by sensing the light that is striking on the receiver of the said sensor (Rajesh, 2020). The flow rate sensor will work by having a rotor placed into a tube and it will measure the rate of flow (Sanjeev, 2018) that may enter into the innards of the circuitries inside Buoyani in order to avert damage. Alongside with the flow rate sensor is the liquid sensor, which will cooperate with the functionality of the flow rate sensor (Tutorialspoint, 2021).

Figure 3.13: The flow rate sensor, the liquid sensor, and the turbidity sensor.
(Sources: Circuitdigest.com, Maker.pro, and Tutorialspoint.com)

Analysis of Power Sources

Solar Panels

Solar panels collect clean renewable energy in the form of sunlight and convert that light into electricity to provide power for electrical devices. The panels contain several individual cells composed of layers of silicon or phosphorous that provides the negative charge, and boron for the positive charge. They work under the photovoltaic effect, which happens when the panel starts absorbing the photons to initiate an electric current. Subsequent energy produced from photons hitting the surface of the panel allows electrons to be released into the electric field generated by the cells which pull these free electrons into a directional current (MrSolar.com, 2021).

Figure 3.14: A solar panel used for homes. (Source: Publicdomainpictures.net)

Hydro Rotors

According to the patency document of Elias - Reyes (1986), a hydro rotor is a hydrodynamically contoured tank having a longitudinal axis and being shaped with forward and rear pointed ends to provide low drag when positioned in water and relative motion exists between said tank and said water.

This can be used in power systems operable in water with propulsion structures for driving objects, such as ships, submarines and torpedoes, through the water characteristically have a power - driven rotary propeller or screw positioned at the ship's blunt ends.

In addition, there is a stabilizer that is meant to be mounted to and protracted amongst forward and rear pointed ends and at controlled radial positions to stabilize directional movement.

Figure 3.15: A mobile hydro rotor that is being deployed in the water.
(Source: Pinterest)

Surveillance Systems

Hidden Cameras

There are many ways in order to record details of what is happening inside a Buoyani unit. However, the researchers deem that the most efficient way to handle this is by using camera traps. The World Wildlife Fund (WWF) states that a camera trap is simply a digital camera connected to an infrared sensor which can “see” warm objects that are moving, like animals. When an animal moves past the sensor it causes the camera to fire, recording an image or video to the memory card for later retrieval. Camera traps can be left in the field to continuously watch an area of habitat for weeks or even months, recording the rarest events which occur in nature. This can include everything from a big cat patrolling its territory, to the raiding of a bird’s nest by a predator. Camera traps are also “wildlife friendly”, in that they cause little or no disturbance to wildlife. At the same time, they produce permanent and verifiable records of animals, akin to traditional museum voucher specimens.

Figure 3.16: A modern camera trap that is deployed in forests. (Source: WWF)

In the Buoyani project, the Buoyani units are intended to be placed with a more secure camera trap if ever someone gets near the unit. The cameras will be placed in areas where someone does not expect it to where it should be, in order to evade any encounters with dismantling the device.

This in turn will let Team Maharlika choose two options, the first one being pre recorded images and videos that are saved by a memory card of the device, then fetching it off in order to get the data collected, or the second option being the one where the Buoyani unit sends it through the introduced communication payloads, with a slight guarantee of a data loss if ever a jamming of the signals happen in such circumstances. A third option however, may integrate both of them for the efficiency of the data that is being collected through the device.

Designs

Initial Illustrations of Buoyani

The initial illustrations of Project Buoyani were sketched by Cassia Cyrus Olmon, one of the members of Team Maharlika. Improvements for these drawings were done by the author of this paper.

Figure 3.17 - 3.18: The first initial design sketches for Project Buoyani. (Source: Cassia Cyrus Olmon, Team Maharlika)

Improvements for the designs of the initial sketch of Project Buoyani was then proceeded again by Cassia Cyrus Olmon. This time, Project Buoyani has been given more emphasis to the parts and colors of the project to indicate the parts of the buoy that is to be designed.

Figure 3.19 - 3.22: Slight revisions for the initial designs of Project Buoyani.
(Source: Cassia Cyrus Olmon, Team Maharlika)

The improvements for these illustrations were designed in Adobe Illustrator CC 2019 and Adobe Photoshop CC 2019. These sketches would then be the blueprints for the said buoy project.

Figure 3.23: Digital remastering on the revisions for Project Buoyani.
(Source: Marc Andrie Bermundo, Team Maharlika)

Computer - Aided Designs (CAD)

The computer aided designs of Project Buoyani are designed both by the author of this study and Julius Rafael Ele in the program, Autodesk Fusion 360.

Figure 3.24 - 3.30: The stages of computer - aided design (CAD) development of the upper, lower, and full body of Project Buoyani in Autodesk Fusion 360. (Sources: Marc Andrie Bermundo, Julius Rafael Ele, Team Maharlika)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following technologies that are being discussed in this paper will all be used in the Buoyani as of the writing of this paper. As the Buoyani project is a sensor buoys system that integrates sensor fusion, all of the sensors that will be commercially brought when creating this project will be stated here at this section.

The following materials for the sensors are already set upon and decided by Team Maharlika. Any information regarding how will the product will come to fruition will be private as of this paper's writing.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concludes that the materials used for Project Buoyani is efficient and low-cost. However, supplementary material analysis and real demonstrations once the pandemic is over shall be measured as a priority if the project continues soon after the recession of the Novel Coronavirus 2019 or COVID-19.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to give thanks to the tactless mentors of the Senior High School Department and the Science Department for their intransigent views on letting us to be delayed or to be postponed in creating this paper. This slowed down a whole lot in our write-ups and forms, especially for a contest that they contracted us to join. This is also added by the fact that they have acted upon as the major hindrance of our road in the corporate world, which adds to the insult. I also would like to give an appreciation to my laptop named Rogue, she never gave up.

Another thing is that, I would like to stress out that any connection on our team will be noted as void in the following months, when we graduate. What happened to us here is terrible. I personally wouldn't want my juniors to suffer more because our batch (and particularly us) are talented. Neither my leader Erwin nor Justin don't want this situation either. Acting like this is easy for the students while not giving them something that is totally just in return. Terrific.

RECOMMENDATIONS

As this paper is a research based on an ongoing project, the recommendations will not be presented here in this paper. Instead, all of the recommendation will be notified within the communications of our team.

PHOTO CREDITS

The pictures and screenshots that are present in this paper are of Marc Andrie Bermundo.

Other pictures that are shown have been tagged in with a source enclosed under a pair of parentheses. Illustrations of the buoy (drawing and by using Autodesk Fusion 360) are of Cassia Cyrus Olmon, Marc Andrie Bermundo, and Julius Rafael Ele.

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